

Spectral and Magnetic Studies on Bivalent Metal Complexes of some Monoprotic Tridentate Ligands

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Six-coordinated chelates of the type $[M(L)_2]$ and $[M(L')_3]$ were synthesised, where $M = Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} ; $LH = o-(N-\alpha\text{-furfuralideneimino})\text{ethane sulphonic acid}$; and $L'H = o-(N-\alpha\text{-furfuralideneimino})\text{benzene sulphonic acid}$. These compounds have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight, conductance, magnetic and spectroscopic data. Various spectroscopic parameters, viz. $10 Dq, B, \nu_2/\nu_1$ and λ have also been evaluated. The two ligands are structurally similar and behave as monoprotic tridentates.

A variety of metal chelates of polydentates have been reported¹⁻⁸ earlier. In the present communication, we report the findings of the investigation on $Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} chelates of $o-(N-\alpha\text{-furfuralideneimino})\text{ethane sulphonic acid}$ (HFE) and $o-(N-\alpha\text{-furfuralideneimino})\text{benzene sulphonic acid}$ (HFB).

Experimental

HFE and HFB were synthesised by refluxing equimolar ethanolic solutions of furfural-2-aldehyde and taurine or orthanilic acid in presence of piperidine as a condensing agent for 2-3 h. The mixture was then filtered hot. The filtrate on cooling gave solid mass from which pure crystals of HFE and HFB were obtained on recrystallisation from ethanol. The ligands were characterised by elemental analysis, molecular wt. and ir spectra (HFE, m.p. 197° and HFB, m.p. 224°). The metal nitrates and other solvents used were of AnalaR grade.

Synthesis of metal complexes: Equimolar quantities of metal acetates and ligand were refluxed in ethanol (15-20 ml) for 3-4 h on a steam-bath. The clear solutions gave a solid mass on cooling. It was recrystallised to give pure crystals (70-75%)

The solid chelates were subjected to elemental analysis for metal, nitrogen and sulphur. A Gallenkamp semimicro ebulliometer was used to determine the mol. wt. in dioxane. A Hilger-UVISPEC spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of electronic spectra in donor and non-donor solvents. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded using NaCl prism.

Results and Discussion

The thermogravimetric analysis of the chelates showed no weight-loss at 120-180°, but decomposed

at 290-340° to metal oxides. It showed that water molecules were not loosely held but occupied coordination positions in the metal complexes.

From analytical data stoichiometry of the complexes were found to be $[M(L)_2]$ or $[M(L')_3]$, where $M = Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II} ; $LH = (C_7H_9NO_4S)$ and $L'H = (C_{11}H_9NO_4S)$. Their molar conductance in MeOH ($10^{-3} M$) were in the range 2.3-9.6 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2$ suggesting non-electrolytic nature⁹ of the complexes.

The electronic spectra of the metal complexes were recorded both in donor (pyridine) and non-donor (benzene) solvents. For the Fe^{II} chelate, only one transition ${}^6T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^6E_g(D)$ was observed revealing its octahedral stereochemistry.

In the case of Co^{II} complexes ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ band splitted into two or more components due to lifting of degeneracy of ${}^4T_{1g}$ level either by the spin-orbital coupling or by the presence of a low symmetry component in the ligand-field. However, the values of $10 Dq, B$ and ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.84-1.90), and chocolate-red colour and magnetic moments of these complexes supported octahedral geometry⁷. Ni^{II} complexes displayed three transitions (Table 1) indicative of octahedral stereochemistry.

Spectral data are utilised to compute the various ligand field parameters⁸, such as $10 Dq, B, \nu_2/\nu_1$, and using the ligand field theory of spin-allowed transitions in d^8 configuration. $10 Dq$ and B values for Ni^{II} chelates indicated strong ligand fields giving rise to reasonably strong covalent bonds. The high values of $10 Dq$ and B were consistent with the coordination by nitrogen of azomethine group⁸. The ν_2/ν_1 value of 1.91-2.03, and yellowish-green colour and their magnetic moment of the triquo-complexes suggested octahedral geometry.

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC TRANSITIONS (IN cm^{-1}), MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND RELEVANT SPECTROSCOPIC PARAMETERS* OF COMPLEXES OF HFE and HFB

Metal chelate	Transition	Extinction coefficient ϵ $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Wave no. ν	μ_{eff} B.M. at 303 K	10 Dq	B cm^{-1}	ν_2/ν_1	10 Dq/B	λ cm^{-1}
MnII	—	—	—	5.80 (5.84)	2 950 (3 130)	730 (768)	1.146 (1.163)	4.04 (4.07)	610 (617)
FeII	${}^4T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(D)$	60(72)	10 770(10 950)	5.95 (5.47)	—	—	—	—	—
CoII	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$	72(85)	8 900(9 120)	4.89 (5.05)	8 060 (7 680)	764 (726)	1.905 (1.942)	10.54 (10.57)	225 (263)
	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$	81(92)	16 900(16 800)						
	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$	87(98)	21 200(21 450)						
NiII	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$	78(87)	8 800(9 250)	3.10 (3.28)	9 150 (8 430)	1 150 (1 055.3)	2.039 (1.911)	7.95 (7.98)	309 (335)
	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	86(99)	17 950(17 680)						
	${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$	95(100)	25 700(25 900)						
CuII	${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$	110(125)	11 500(11 760)	1.80 (1.83)	3 500 (3 580)	266.6 (217.3)	1.304 (1.314)	13.12 (16.49)	306 (176)
	${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2E_g$	115(132)	15 000(15 340)						
	$C \rightarrow T$		23 500(23 200)						

* Data on HFB—metal chelates are shown in paranthesis.

In case of Cu^{II} complexes, three intense bands ($\epsilon \approx 10^3 - 10^4$) were observed. The broadness and position of the bands indicated tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry. The ratio $\nu_{\text{Cu}}/\nu_{\text{Ni}}$ for HFE and HFB were found to be 1.30 and 1.27, respectively, indicating⁹ that $[\text{Cu}(\text{FE})_2]$ was more tetragonally distorted than $[\text{Cu}(\text{FB})_2]$ in terms of Jahn—Teller effect¹⁰.

Ir spectra: The two bands at 1 150—1 140 and 1 620—1 600 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of HFE and HFB were assigned to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{SO}_3\text{H})$ and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. In the spectra of the metal complexes, the 1 150—1 140 cm^{-1} band disappeared, suggesting coordination through the sulphonate group. The 1 620—1 600 cm^{-1} ligand bands shifted to the lower frequency side in the complexes suggesting participation of $>\text{C=N}$ moiety in complexation. Two new bands at 550—530 and 440—410 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the metal complexes were assigned to M—O and M—N bondings¹¹, respectively.

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